

Some Mixed-ligand Hydridocarbonyl and Hydridophosphine Complexes of Ruthenium(II) and Iridium(III)

R. N. PANDEY*, SUNIL KUMAR, ARUN KUMAR and SHASHI KANT KUMAR

P. G. Centre of Chemistry (M.U.), College of Commerce, Patna-800 020

Manuscript received 22 January 1992, revised 16 December 1992, accepted 19 February 1993

Mixed-ligand hydridocarbonyl and hydridophosphine complexes of Ru^{II} and Ir^{III} have been isolated from the displacement reaction of [RuH(CO)(Pφ₃)₃Cl] with ligand isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INAH) in benzene medium. Most probable structures are assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, electronic, infrared and far-infrared spectral studies. In all cases bonding of INAH occurs through amino nitrogen of hydrazine residue.

Hydridocarbonyl and hydridophosphine complexes of ruthenium(II)¹ and iridium(III)² have been studied by several workers. They are unique and having interesting insights into bonding, structure and reactivity of molecules which generally undergo displacement reaction in solution³. In view of these features, the present paper involves the study of displacement reaction of [RuH(CO)(Pφ₃)₃Cl] in benzene which was isolated by Agarwala and Poddar⁴ in different isomeric forms.

Results and Discussion

When replacement reactions of the pink isomer of [RuH(CO)(Pφ₃)₃Cl] with isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INAH) is carried out in benzene medium, two of the coordinated Pφ₃ molecules are replaced by two ligand (INAH) molecules to give yellowish

light brown compound [RuH(CO)(Pφ₃)(INAH)₂Cl] (Table 1). But in the similar condition the yellow isomer of [RuH(CO)(Pφ₃)₃Cl] yields leaf brown colour compound [RuH(CO)(Pφ₃)₂(INAH)Cl]. The bonded hydride ion, chlorine and carbonyl group are not replaced. The C≡O and Pφ₃ groups have large *trans*-effect and the two replaced Pφ₃ molecules must have been present in the position *trans* to C≡O group and one of the three Pφ₃ groups in the [RuH(CO)(Pφ₃)₃Cl] molecule. This has been found true experimentally in the present case. All products obtained after carrying out substitution reactions are nonconducting and diamagnetic having octahedral configuration arising from *d²sp³*-hybridisation.

Iridium(III) compounds are also diamagnetic but molar conductivities in DMF were found to be

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Molar cond Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	λ _{max} (cm ⁻¹) (Assignment)
		C	H	N	M	Cl		
1	40-45	53.23	4.27	12.34	15.01	5.16	8.42	
		(53.03)	4.28	11.97	14.39	5.06)		
2	—	62.06	4.50	4.48	12.64	4.28	5.24	
		(62.43)	4.59	5.08	12.22	4.29)		
3	122	60.30	4.41	3.56	15.32	81.80	81.80	46 513 (CT)
		(60.24)	4.36	3.45	15.80)	—		38 023 (¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g})
4	215	47.00	4.00	15.32	18.02	6.69	89.48	45 455 (CT)
		(46.96)	4.09	15.64	17.87	6.61)		37 594 (¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g})
5	120	51.62	4.20	—	22.21	8.68	3.62	47 619(CT)
		(51.03)	4.25	—	22.07	8.16)		38 462(¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g})

81.80 and 89.98 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for $[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{INAH})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{IrH}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{INAH})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ respectively, indicating the presence of three ions. However, DMF solution of $[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was found to be nonconducting indicating that Cl-atoms in this complex are coordinated.

Electronic spectra of all the iridium(III) compounds are almost identical with a very strong broad band near 46513 cm^{-1} and medium band around 38 023 cm^{-1} . The first band is of charge transfer (CT) origin and the second band arises due to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ transition⁵. Moreover, the charge transfer band is of such high intensity that it blots out other ligand field bands in other expected regions. Probably the magnitude of ligand field is considerably enhanced by bonding $\text{P}\phi_3$ ligand which causes spm-paired complex and the CT band obscure $d-d$ transitions. Thus, octahedral structure of all the Ir^{III} compounds may be suggested following previous literature⁵.

The ir spectrum of $\text{P}\phi_3$ has been interpreted by Deacon and Green⁶. A close examination of spectrum of $\text{P}\phi_3$, INAH, Ru^{II} and Ir^{III} compounds indicates the following. Three bands of medium intensity observed at 3 400, 3 310 and 3 210 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of INAH assigned to ν_{NH_2} , ν_{asymNH} , ν_{symNH} respectively, are red-shifted (80–100 cm^{-1}) in the spectra of the Ru^{II} and Ir^{III} compounds suggesting bonding of INAH through amino nitrogen atom of hydrazine residue⁷. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ mixed with $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ observed as strong band at 1 420 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of INAH also red-shifted (40–50 cm^{-1}) in all the complexes indicating increase in CN bond order due to bonding through amino nitrogen atom of hydrazine residue of INAH. The strong band at 1 640 cm^{-1} due to NH_2 deformation associated with OCN bending mode also red-shifted (20 cm^{-1}) supporting bonding through amino nitrogen atom. The ν_{CO} band of INAH observed at 1 680 cm^{-1} remains almost unchanged indicating the absence of bonding through carbonyl oxygen.

The medium intensity bands at 2 060 and 720 cm^{-1} in $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{INAH})_2\text{Cl}]$ and at 1 980 and 715 cm^{-1} in $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{INAH})\text{Cl}]$ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ru-H}}$ and $\delta_{\text{Ru-H}}$ ⁸. It appears that Ru-H bond in $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{INAH})_2\text{Cl}]$ is stronger than

Ru-H bond in $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{INAH})\text{Cl}]$ as $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group has much greater *trans*-effect than Cl. Further, the $\nu \text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ band in $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{INAH})_2\text{Cl}]$ appears as sharp medium intensity bands at 1 890 and 1 820 cm^{-1} but weak band 1 910 cm^{-1} in the case of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{INAH})\text{Cl}]$. Most probably much less interaction between $\text{P}\phi_3$ group and $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group occurs in $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{INAH})\text{Cl}]$. The fact is substantiated by the splitting of $\nu \text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ band in the spectrum of $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{INAH})_2\text{Cl}]$.

Medium intensity bands observed at 1 950 and 720 cm^{-1} in $[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{INAH})]\text{Cl}_2$ and at 2 050 and 750 cm^{-1} in $[\text{IrH}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{INAH})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ir-H}}$ and $\delta_{\text{Ir-H}}$ ⁹. Chatt *et al.*¹⁰ found that M-H stretching mode is sensitive to other ligands, particularly in the *trans* position. In the present case, $\nu_{\text{Ir-H}}$ is much more affected by $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group *trans* to Ir-H bond. The lower position of $\nu_{\text{Ir-H}}$ in the $[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{INAH})]\text{Cl}_2$ is due to stronger *trans*-position of $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group than $\text{P}\phi_3$ group. Thus, octahedral structure may be the most reasonable structure. The $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group *trans* to hydrogen atom is also assumed in octahedral structure of $[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by considering the position of $\nu \text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ band which appears at 2 200 and 1 890 cm^{-1} . This is further supported¹¹ by the presence of $\nu_{\text{Ir-Cl}}$ modes observed at 460 cm^{-1} . The position of $\nu_{\text{Ir-Cl}}$ modes at 315 cm^{-1} also suggests that two chlorine atoms are *trans* to each other. The position of $\nu_{\text{Ir-Cl}}$ is observed generally at 276 cm^{-1} or below if chlorine is *trans* to $\text{P}\phi_3$ ¹².

All mixed hydridocarbonyl complexes of Ru^{II} with INAH also contain some new bands in their far-infrared spectra. The $\nu_{\text{Ru-N}}$ (480–485), $\nu_{\text{Ru-Cl}}$ (440–370), $\nu_{\text{Ru-P}}$ (270–240), $\nu_{\text{Ir-N}}$ (390) and $\nu_{\text{Ir-P}}$ (310 cm^{-1}) bands are in good agreement with the previous observations¹³.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. or C.P. grade. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INAH) (E. Merck) was used after crystallisation. Its purity was checked spectroscopically. $[\text{RuH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ was prepared by the method of Agarwala and Poddar⁴.

Hydridochlorocarbonyltriphenylphosphinebis-

(isonicotinic acid hydrazide)ruthenium(II). $[RuH(CO)(P\phi_3)(INAH)_2Cl]$ (1) : To the pink isomer of $[RuH(CO)(P\phi_3)_3Cl]$ (0.5 g) dissolved in benzene (30 ml), ethanolic solution of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (0.2 g) was added. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was heated on a water-bath till the volume of the mixture was reduced to ~ 20 ml. The contents were treated with a mixture of ether containing ethanol and then cooled in a refrigerator. The resulting yellowish light brown coloured solid was washed with ether and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Hydridochlorocarbonylbis(triphenylphosphie)isonicotinic acid hydrazide ruthenium(II). $[RuH(CO)(P\phi_3)_2(INAH)Cl]$ (2) : It was prepared as mentioned above using the yellow isomer of $[RuH(CO)(P\phi_3)_3Cl]$. A leaf brown coloured solid was obtained.

Hydridocarbonyltris(triphenylphosphine)isonicotinic acid hydrazide iridium(III) chloride. $[IrH(CO)(P\phi_3)_3(INAH)Cl_2]$ (3) : To a suspension of triphenyl phosphine (5 mmol) and KOH (3 mmol) in ethanol (100 ml), a solution of $IrCl_3$ (1 mmol) was added slowly with stirring and further stirred at 60° for 2 h and then cooled. The separated solid was dissolved into benzene, then mixed with ethanolic solution of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (3 mmol) and again stirred 1 h at 60° . On cooling the mixture, yellowish red crystals were obtained which were washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Hydridotriphenylphosphinetetrakis(isonicotinic acid hydrazide)iridium(III) chloride. $[IrH(P\phi_3)(INAH)_4Cl_2]$ (4) : A mixture of ethanolic solutions of $IrCl_3$ (6 mmol), $P\phi_3$ (6 mmol) and INAH (4 mmol) was stirred at 85° for 1 h. It was then cooled to room temperature and two drops of concentrated HCl were added. The resulting light yellowish brown coloured solid was washed several time with ice-cold ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Hydridodichlorobis(triphenyl phosphine)iridium(III) trihydrate. $[IrH(CO)(P\phi_3)_2Cl_2].3H_2O$ (5) : A saturated aqueous solution of $IrCl_3$ (1 mmol) and KCl (3 mmol) was slowly added with vigorous stirring

in an ethanolic solution of triphenyl phosphine (6 mmol) containing KOH (3 mmol) at 60° . After stirring the mixture for 2 h, when a light pink coloured solid was separated on standing the mixture at room temperature. The solid separated was suspended in monoethyl ether of ethylene glycol. The solvent was then removed on a water-bath. It was further mixed with methanol and a few drops of benzene. The resulting light pink coloured solid was washed with ice-cold methanol and kept in a desiccator for drying.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were done at U.S.I.C., Delhi. Analyses of metals¹⁴ and chlorine¹⁵ were carried out using standard methods. Infrared and electronic spectra were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic measurements were made by Gouy method at room temperature (300 K). Calibration was done using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the standard. The conductivities of the complexes were measured in DMF solution with the help of a Sistrionic conductometer.

References

1. J. CHATT, B. L. SHAW and A. E. FIELD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 3466; G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 1711; T. A. STEPHENSON and G. WILKINSON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 945; M. S. LUPIN and B. L. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 741.
2. M. ANGOLETTA, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1963, **93**, 1343; J. CHATT, R. S. COFFEY and B. L. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 7391; J. K. NICHOLSON and B. L. SHAW, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1965, 3533; J. M. JENKINS and B. L. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1407.
3. B. SINGH and M. CHANDRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 676.
4. U. AGARWALA and R. K. PODDAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 477.
5. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1957, **11**, 151; H. H. SCHMIDTKA and D. GARTHOFF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1317; G. L. GEOFFROY, M. S. WRIGHTON, G. S. HAMMOND, and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 430.
6. G. B. DEACON and J. H. S. GREEN, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1968, **24**, 845.
7. C. B. MAHATO, *Acta Cienca India*, 1978, **4**, 3.
8. J. CHATT, B. L. SHAW and A. E. FIELD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 3466; H. D. KAESZ and R. B. SAILLANT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **72**, 231; G. K. N. REDDY, M. N. NANCE and GOWDA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 185.
9. S. S. BATH, and L. VASKA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963,

- 85, 3500; J. CHATT, N. P. JOHNSON, and B. L. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3371; L. VASKA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 4100.
10. J. CHATT, L. A. DUNCANSON and B. L. SHAW, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1958, 859.
11. B. L. SHAW and A. C. SMITHIES, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1047.
12. J. M. JENKINS and B. L. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 6789.
13. K. H. SCHMIDT and A. MÜLLER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1976, 19, 41; J. M. FLETCHER, W. E. GARDNER, A. FOX and G. TOPPING, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1038; M. L. BRUCE and F. G. A. STONE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 1238; C. A. REED and ROPER, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 1370; W. P. GRIFFITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 899.
14. P. C. RAY and N. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 251.
15. F. P. TREADWELL and W. T. HALL, "Analytical Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1935, Vol. II, p. 307.